

CONTRASTS: PROVIDING INSIGHT INTO THE DESIGN OF
EFFICIENT INDUSTRIAL EXPERIMENTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses a tool, contrasts, useful in identifying an efficient (economical) set of experimental runs in what might otherwise be a full factorial experiment. Contrasts may also be used to analyze the data that comes out of the experiment, but more efficient tools are available for that task.

The easiest way to learn about contrasts, however, is by applying them to the analysis of data. Insights from that application facilitate the understanding of how contrasts contribute to identifying an efficient set of experimental runs.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of "designing" an experiment is to preclude doing any more testing than is absolutely necessary. This will minimize the time and cost needed to accomplish the objectives of the experiment. It is presumed that the objectives of the experiment are, first, to distinguish the active factors from the inactive factors with regard to some response variable; second, to determine the optimum values for the active factors in order to optimize the response.

"Factors" are also known as parameters, process variables, and

independent variables. The "response variable" is sometimes called the quality characteristic or dependent variable.

This subject matter is covered in the AFIT School of Systems and Logistics Professional Continuing Education course "Advanced Process Control Methods" (QMT 089). The purpose of the course is to present a practical approach to understanding and using design of experiments (DOE), primarily to benefit the Air Force R&D community (including the contractors).

DOE is a tool developed in the West but not widely used in industry until popularized by Dr. Genichi Taguchi of Japan. DOE is now in widespread use in Japanese industry and has been gaining increasing favor in the United States in recent years.

The use of contrasts as a design of experiments teaching tool is emphasized by Dr. Donald J. Wheeler in his course and book entitled "Understanding Industrial Experimentation." The concept of contrasts and the application presented in this paper are from Dr. Wheeler's book, with some modification, additions, and analysis. As a student of Dr. Wheeler's and a teacher of his methods, it is an honor to attempt to convey his insights further.

USING CONTRASTS FOR ANALYSIS

Consider the following experiment. We want to study the performance of four laboratories in performing a particular test. Twenty samples are prepared from one batch and five samples are sent for analysis to each lab. This experiment has a single "factor" (laboratory), which has four qualitative "levels" (labs A, B, C, and D). The response variable is the percent of dissolved potassium measured by each laboratory. Each laboratory's data constitutes a "subgroup" of size five ($n = 5$).

Two of the laboratories are Air Force labs (A and B) and two are contractor labs (C and D). We would like to compare, i.e., contrast, the labs in any of several different pairings. For example:

- 1) How does one Air Force lab (A) compare with another (B)?
- 2) How does one contractor lab (C) compare with another (D)?
- 3) How do the Air Force labs, on average, compare with the contractor labs?
- 4) How does one lab (D) compare with the average of the others (A, B, and C)?

We are not trying to determine goodness. There is no known true value of percent dissolved potassium. Rather, we are trying to determine if there are significant differences in the subgroup averages. Contrasts and the F-ratio make these comparisons.

A set of coefficients that define the first three of the comparisons (contrasts) above are:

Lab	A	B	C	D
<u>Contrast</u>	c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4
1. A vs B	1	-1	0	0
2. C vs D	0	0	1	-1
3. A,B vs C,D	1	1	-1	-1

Note: Certain rules were followed in defining coefficients above. The sum of the coefficients for any contrast must be zero. Any subgroup (lab) not involved in the contrast is assigned a coefficient of zero. The coefficients of any contrast can be multiplied by any non-zero number and remain a contrast, but it's best to keep it simple.

Suppose the lab data is as follows:

DATA SET:

Lab	A	B	C	D
Values	55.9	58.7	60.7	62.7
	56.1	61.4	60.3	64.5
	57.3	60.9	60.9	63.1
	55.2	59.1	61.4	59.2
	58.1	58.2	62.3	60.3
Avg s_2	56.52	59.66	61.12	61.96
s^2	1.352	1.983	0.592	4.668

EVALUATING A CONTRAST

To begin analyzing the data, we compute the "estimated value for the contrast", $\hat{c}$, by multiplying each subgroup average by its corresponding coefficient and summing the resulting values. So,

$$\hat{c}_1 = 56.52 - 59.66 + 0 + 0 = -3.14$$

$$\hat{c}_2 = 0 + 0 + 61.12 - 61.96 = -.084$$

$$\hat{c}_3 = 56.52 + 59.66 - 61.12 - 61.96 = -6.9$$

IS THE CONTRAST SIGNIFICANT?

If the estimated contrast value, $\hat{c}$, is far from zero, the contrast is significant, i.e, the difference in subgroup averages is considered detectable. If it is close to zero, the contrast is not significant. To "draw the line" between significance and non-significance, we use the F-ratio.

$$F\text{-ratio} = MSB/MSW = MS(C)/MSW$$

(where MSB, MSW, and MS(C) are the Mean Square Between, the Mean Square Within, and the Mean Square for the contrast)

To compute the MS(C) requires a SS(C) (Sum of Squares for the contrast) value and degrees of freedom value:

$$MS(C) = SS(C)/d.f.$$

Every contrast will have exactly one degree of freedom because it is a linear combination of subgroup averages. Thus, the Mean Square is merely the Sum of Squares for that contrast:

$$MS(C) = SS(C)/d.f. = SS(C)$$

So, F-ratio = SS(C)/MSW

To compute SS(C), the numerator of the F-ratio, use:

$$SS(C) = (\hat{c})^2/\text{adjustment term}$$

The adjustment term compensates for the fact that, as stated above, we are free to multiply a row of contrast coefficients by any non-zero value. To compute the adjustment term for this experiment, average the squared coefficients. That is:

$$\text{adjustment term} = (\sum c_j^2)/n$$

Thus, the adjustment term for the first contrast is:

$$(1 + 1 + 0 + 0) / 5 = 0.4$$

The second and third contrasts have adjustment terms of 0.4 and 0.8, respectively. The three SS(C) values are then 24.65, 1.76, and 59.51, respectively.

The denominator of the F-ratio for a contrast is the MSW, which comes from the One-Way ANOVA table (which is determined from the data set to be):

ONE-WAY ANOVA TABLE:

<u>Source</u>	<u>SS</u>	<u>d.f.</u>	<u>MS</u>
Between	85.925	3	28.64
Within	34.38	16	2.15
Total	120.30	19	

So, MSW = 2.15 and we compute:

<u>Contrast</u>	<u>F-ratio</u>
1. A vs B	11.47*
2. C vs D	0.82
3. A,B vs C,D	27.68*

* Each of these F-ratios exceeds the .05 level of significance critical F-value (for 1 and 16 degrees of freedom) of approximately 4.5. That is, contrasts 1 and 3 are said to be significant.

The significant F-ratios suggest that the two Air Force laboratories have detectably different averages of percent dissolved potassium. They also suggest that the Air Force labs, collectively, have detectably different averages than the team of two contractor labs.

INTERPRETING THE CONTRASTS

What about quantifying these interpretations? To do this we introduce the notion of the estimated contrast effect, $\hat{l}$ (l-hat). It will be the estimate of the difference between the averages of the two groups compared by the contrast. So,

$$\hat{l} = \hat{c} / \text{Sum of positive } c_j\text{'s}$$

Then, we get:

<u>Contrast</u>	$\hat{c}$	$\hat{l}$
1. A vs B	-3.14	-3.14
3. A,B vs C,D	-6.90	-3.45

Thus, Air Force Lab (B) averages 3.14 percentage points dissolved potassium higher than its counterpart Lab (A). Similarly, the contractor team averages 3.45 percentage points higher than the two Air Force Labs as a group.

It may be noted that these l-hat values could have been derived more quickly from the subgroup averages. Indeed, the use of contrasts as a computation device is very "pedestrian," as Dr. Wheeler says. With the software available today, we needn't be concerned with the lack of manual computation speed inherent with contrasts.

However, the concept of contrasts is the basis for many useful facets of ANOVA, including an understanding of the built-in redundancies of full factorial experiments, which we will now begin to discuss.

MULTIFACTOR ANOVA

Contrasts are helpful in understanding the development of

fractional factorial and screening designs. That's what makes contrasts appealing from a teaching viewpoint.

The total SS (SST) may be partitioned into a Between SS (SSB) plus a Within SS (SSW) (single partition or "One-Way" ANOVA) i.e.,

$$SST = SSB + SSW$$

In addition, the SSB can sometimes be partitioned into k-1 independent parts, where k is the number of subgroups. This latter partitioning is only possible, however, when the source of SSB is a set of mutually orthogonal (independent) contrasts.

Contrasts that are "orthogonal" to one another make comparisons (contrasts) that are independent of each other. For a set of k subgroups, the largest number of mutually orthogonal contrasts is k-1. A set of k-1 mutually orthogonal contrasts is a "maximal" mutually orthogonal set of contrasts. The set of three contrasts shown above for the four labs (k = 4 subgroups) is such a set.

The mutual orthogonality can be demonstrated by multiplying each pair of contrasts and noting that the products of corresponding coefficients satisfy the rules for being a contrast:

				<u>Contrast?</u>
1x2:	0	0	0	Yes
1x3:	1	-1	0	Yes
2x3:	0	0	-1	Yes

Recall from the One-Way ANOVA table that SSB = 85.925. This is, not coincidentally, also the sum of the three SS(C)'s, i.e.,

$$24.649 + 1.764 + 59.5125 = 85.925$$

Contrasts 1-3 decompose the SSB into single degree-of-freedom components. The resulting ANOVA table is:

SINGLE DEGREE OF FREEDOM ANOVA:

<u>Source</u>	<u>SS</u>	<u>d.f.</u>	<u>MS</u>	<u>F</u>
A vs B	24.65	1	24.65	11.47
C vs D	1.76	1	1.76	0.82
A,B vs C,D	59.51	1	59.51	27.68
Within	34.38	16	2.15	
Total	120.30	19		

A so-called "factorial ANOVA table" is developed by collapsing a Single Degree of Freedom ANOVA table into rows that represent each main effect and the interaction effects. This experiment has only one main effect because it has only one factor. It has no interaction effects because it has only one factor. Thus the factorial ANOVA table is the same as the One-Way ANOVA table shown above:

FACTORIAL ANOVA TABLE:

<u>Source</u>	<u>SS</u>	<u>d.f.</u>	<u>MS</u>
Between	85.925	3	28.64
Within	34.38	16	2.15
Total	120.30	19	

A factorial ANOVA table is invariant in the sense that the same result comes from any set of maximal mutually orthogonal contrasts. A different set of maximal mutually orthogonal contrasts for the lab data would be as follows:

Lab	A	B	C	D
<u>Contrast</u>	<u>C₁</u>	<u>C₂</u>	<u>C₃</u>	<u>C₄</u>
4. A vs C	1	0	-1	0
5. B vs D	0	1	0	-1
6. A,C vs B,D	1	-1	1	-1

Again, to verify mutual orthogonality, we multiply each contrast by each other and note that the products of corresponding coefficients constitute a contrast:

					<u>Contrast?</u>
4x5	0	0	0	0	Yes
4x6	1	0	-1	0	Yes
5x6	0	-1	0	1	Yes

Each row is a contrast, so the set is mutually orthogonal and since, $k-1 = 3$, maximal.

The $\hat{c}$ values are respectively: -4.6, -2.3, and -3.98, so:

SS(C) values are correspondingly: 52.9, 13.32, and 19.80, which sum to same value as the first set of contrasts (85.925 except for rounding error).

CONCLUSION

The invariance of the factorial table is very important. Since any maximal mutually orthogonal set of contrasts gives the same result, why perform a factorial set of experimental runs? Why not preclude redundancy in the name of efficiency? That's what a designed experiment is and that is how contrasts relate to understanding the beginning of designed experiments.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

Wheeler, Donald J., Understanding Industrial Experimentation, Second Edition, (SPC Press, 1990).